

Re-Creating ‘Natural’ Heritage: Landscape Perception and Outdoor Tourism in the Web 2.0

David Casado-Neira

Faculty of Education, University of Vigo

Avd. Castelao s/n

32002 Ourense

Spain

dcneira@uvigo.es

1. Landscape or recreation of environment

Landscape is a very complex phenomenon. Under a geomorphological view landscape is the result of years of progressive and deep changes. Forces of nature are sometimes abrupt and unexpected but the most of the geomorphological transformations are too slow to be appreciated at a simple glance. This view and knowledge of landscape must be done as an expert knowledge, supported with scientific techniques and procedures. Under a historical, economical, cultural, political views landscape can also be explored scientifically as a transformation of territory consequence of human activity. In fact landscape seems to be more the result of a infinity of forces working in a plastic material. But landscape is also much more than a product composed of several layers, it is an aesthetic experience, that what we appreciate as landscape is a view – a cut – of different parts that have some meaning for us (Simmel 270; Turri 218). In short landscape can be defined as “all the visible features of an area of countryside or land, often considered in terms of their aesthetic appeal” (“New Oxford American Dictionary”). Thus we can talk about beautiful (a birch wood), terrifying (a run down city), spoiled (a dried lake) landscapes, keeping in mind that there is some kind of ideal image being used as rule for comparison that leads to aesthetic canons given by social and cultural values. In other words, we could say it as the following, what has value is seen and what is seen has value. Alain Roger says that landscape is not neutral but a social construction, a way of viewing and experiencing a territory that acquires sense to the person by using some artistic patterns socially given (Roger).

Landscape is a way of seeing, a way of recreating environment. The way we see is socially given landscape is a political question (“Foro do Instituto de estudos das identidades”). How a piece of land (water – sea, lake – or sky, I would add) gains an aesthetic value, which patterns are socially reproduced, which institutionally, which belong to minorities or specific groups and which belong to mere individual taste is involved into power forces between social actors.

2. Touristic multi-landscape in the Era of Internet

The aim of this paper is not to discuss and create a theory of perception and landscape but to approach to the perceived value of landscape and to identify what elements give and subtract value to a landscape. Images of landscape are one of the main resources used in the touristic promotion of a place. Tourism is an experience with a deep aesthetic component, and specially for outdoor tourism landscapes plays a central role, thus many outdoors activities such hiking, skiing, hang gliding, etc. are the way of enjoying landscapes: the view can be the reward or at least a very important part of the experience.

A landscape photo is not a neutral representation, it is a socially given view of an environment, taking a picture is not a mere physical procedure; someone takes pictures. A picture of a landscape for touristic promotion is telling us something not only about the environment itself and where the photo was taken, but also about what has value for the touristic promoters.

Nowadays tourism is a wide extended practice in developed economies. Tourism is becoming worldwide a powerful economic activity where touristic consumers have the opportunity to choose between a huge number of destinations. And in recent years we have also seen how the Internet has been entering in our lives and changing the rules of the touristic market. But Internet doesn't mean only new ways of buying products and more access to information; the birth of the web 2.0 (usage of web technologies and not the technologies themselves) (O'Reilly) has changed the ways touristic destinations are represented, or how landscape is recreated. The fact of sharing information on destinations and photos between visitors in on-line services (like Panoramio, Flickr, Spottedbylocals, Qype, etc. plus internet forums or private blogs) is transforming the access to information and the origin of information. Institutions and touristic services are still providing the ground representation of destinations, even marketing campaigns are the more important tool of creating and transmission of landscape as consumer product, but visitors are adding layers of information to these institutional or promotional images of destinations. And landscapes are becoming more complex, richer in meaning and given information. The implicit values of the representation may correspond or vary between images. Let me present a typical example. A photo of a Maldiven Beach with the characteristic attributes: sea, palm tree, sand and no trace of civilization or human presence (see Photo 1).

Photo 1: Maldiven Beach by KingKurt22, 2008 (Creative Commons)

This photo was taken by a visitor and uploaded at Wikimedia Commons which defines itself “a media file repository making available public domain and freely-licensed educational media content (images, sound and video clips) to everyone (Wikimedia Commons).” In spite of this photo being non-commercial and having no promotional purpose, it represents the common image of a paradise island, very common in touristic advertisement. Another photo (see Photo 2), also taken by a visitor and uploaded at Wikimedia Commons show us also a ‘cut’ of a beautiful Maldivian Islands but from a different perspective, in this case a photo to the back (not to the front) in which we can see more human trace.

Photo 2: Photographs from Maldives by Nevit Dilmen, 2008 (Creative Commons)

It is true that the last two photos could be used for promotional purposes; they transmit the ‘feeling’ of the Maldives Islands as touristic destination. But it is possible to add more and more visual layer and more meanings that sometimes will be in harmony with the iconic image of a paradise destination. The next photo (see Photo 3) is also a landscape, but not a picturesque one; a plane crosses the sky over the island. A piece of information is given that would not be normally presented as interesting for visitors.

Photo 3: Photographs from Maldives by Nevit Dilmen, 2008 (Creative Commons)

In short, the values underlying the representations of environment (landscape) lead to different meanings, some of them will be used in institutional representations of environment (i.e. landscape for touristic promotion) and/or in non institutional representations of environment. Depending on the purposes of the social actor (institutional, non institutional) some ‘cuts’ (Photos 1, 2, 3) can be chosen as iconic images. Some of these images can be common for both purposes or the same values and meanings found in the same images, but sometimes the same values and meanings may find a visual representation through other icons (‘what represents paradise, a palm tree or an airplane?’), other times same icons are linked to diver-

gent values (beach: relax or tediousness?) or different values and meanings are relevant (local people at the market or me at the beach?) (see Figure 1). The web 2.0 creates a multilayer representation of environments with crossing values.

Figure 1: Images with meaning for no institutional and institutional representations of environment

Some years ago photo sharing was limited to small groups and audiences. Due to the explosion of possibilities of sharing information on the web, the repository of images from particular in progressively growing and with it the different meanings given to the element chosen to be part of the landscape. My hypothesis is that the richer (more full of meaning) a place is the more interesting it would be for more people – even in the case the underlying values were the same – from the landscape to the multi-landscape. An environment can become a landscape or many, in a single landscape only a voice is talking, in a multi-landscape many voices are constructing it. The tourism industry may profit of it, and we'll find a way of saving natural and cultural heritage making environment deeper in meaning.

3. Applying multi-landscapes concept to outdoor tourism

In March 2009, an organized group of hikers were asked to take some pictures of the nicest, of the most unpleasant and of the most typical images during some outdoor walks in Galicia (Northwest Spain). The aim of this project was to document how hikers perceive landscape in order to research the touristic possibilities of this region.

One of the destinations was a protected area at the border between Portugal and Galicia. In fact this area is comprised of two natural parks at both sides of the border (National Park of Peneda-Gerês with 702.9 km² at the Portuguese side and Natural Park Baixa Limia-Serra do Xurés with km² at the Galician side with 297,6 km²). The park is a highland area with massive granitic outcrops, poor vegetation and with a small population traditionally living off of raising cattle. Granite and water (used also for construction) have played an important role in the image and representation of this area, these two elements being the icons in the images of landscape (see Photo 4, this photo is very similar to one use by the local tourism agency for promotional purposes):

*Photo 4: View of Albufeira da Caniçada – Vila do Gerês – Terras de Bouro
by Own Work the author, s.d. (Creative Commons)*

After analyzing the photos of landscape used by the tourism agencies (Instituto da Conservação da Natureza e da Biodiversidade – in Portugal – and Turgalicia – in Galicia–) for promotion some patterns were found:

- There are three main characteristics: animals, villages and mountains in the distance.
- Animal motives: A limited serial of animal portraits from the common fauna (like *Aquila chrysaetos*, *Vulpes vulpes*, *Rana perez*, *Lutra lutra*...) and photos of cattle herds in open spaces are the third motive attending to the number of cases.
- Human motives: The images play a mayor attention to ‘cuts’ without human presence. If some trace of human presence or civilization is offered it is always with photos of vernacular architecture (in a mystification of folk culture) without human figures. In this case we can find far photos of villages at the mountains or photos of irrelevant singular buildings (stone granaries, bread oven...).
- Mountains in the distance motives: Perhaps the most present and important motive of all three. Due the granitic nature of the ground and the poor vegetation, granite outcrops are the most characteristic element in landscape. Peneda is internationally known as an important rock-climbing destination. Curiously, no climbing mountains are showed, the mountains are always presented as scenery where only the distance plays a role. These images are presented like the paintings of the romanticism, where the forces of the nature can be felt, granite playing the main role.

These are the main motives in the representation of the natural park(s), no significant differences were found between the Portuguese and the Galician landscapes. One thing is true the elements to play with are limited and a cultural similarity can be found on both sides of the border. The institutional landscape is a visit card to visitors, but for us the question now is if the touristic promotion of the region is based on images and

representations with sense, emotionally exciting for the visitors. Our aim is not to detect what elements can be taken in consideration for future promotion campaigns, but to show that it is possible to create a multi-landscape with the same elements gaining in meanings. Thus the web 2.0 makes possible the diversification of representations and spreading then to potential visitors further over the institutional promotions.

Our group of hikers was asked to take some pictures at the natural park under three categories: nice, unpleasant and typical. The intention of using these categories was to detect first, which elements have a more positive and pleasant incidence (assertive icons), which have a negative connotation (no assertive icons), and which are considered the representation of the most characteristic – in some case photos of typical items were also included under the category nice and even unpleasant (reinforcer icons).

Some similarities but also divergences were found between visitors images and institutional ones. This experience showed us that the way territory is perceived and represented (landscape) by the touristic promoters wasn't the same that the 'ones' given by the hikers. Hikers were paying attention to elements, in some cases, also used in touristic promotion, for example in local museums, but, in other cases, to other ones. Initially it was expected that the participants would reproduce the same aesthetic patterns present in the promotional pictures, thus beautiful landscapes according to some ideal images based on common values: pure nature, views with skyline or distance, vernacular architecture and the kind of elements associated to a idealized rural non-urban environment. It is true, some of the images could fulfill the pattern of the existing promotional images and even with a higher artistic intensity, but a majority of the others are introducing not only new and complementary elements on the 'cuts' but also different views.

- Nice (assertive icons): This is the most interesting category for the purposes of promotion, under nice people take the pictures the thing better transmit the esprit of the place and would be more likely shared with other. People like to show the pleasant (nice) and genuine (typical) aspects of the visited place as evidence of being there. Critical images are not very common as souvenir. Under the category nice we can found the conventional pics when photographing mountains in the distance, but not when photographing other motives like other land views, vegetation, or human presence (no animals were photographed, perhaps due to the difficulty of taking these kind of pictures when hiking). If the motive are mountains it reproduces the same schema that the promotional images. Perhaps it is the most archetypical icon, where the socially given images are stronger, due the impact of media, national education and artistic canons. Or in other words the impact and persistence of romanticism in contemporary societies when see natural and/or rural environments. In Photo 5 we may appreciate an example of an conventional image, similar to the ones used for promotional purposes in the use of elements (granite an water) but with regular light conditions.

Photo 5: Serra do Xurés by Juan Carlos del Carmen García, 2009 ©

Photos 6 and 7 are two examples of new elements introduced: vegetation and people as main motives, other motives like water, rivers or fields are also taken into consideration. The visitors are offering a wider view of the park by introducing all these new 'cuts'. It is possible that they are not showing the most characteristic parts of the park, but they provide a more complex image of the environment by introducing complementary elements, not necessary specific of the park, which enlarges our visual experience, and power of landscape evocation. In Photo 7, it is difficult to know if the nicest is the backdrop of the buildings, the idea of sharing a day of walking with other, or both.

Photo 6: Multi-chromatic forest by Marco Quintas, 2009 ©

Photo 7: Salgueiro by Eiras, 2009 ©

- Unpleasant (non assertive icons): The reason for including this atypical category is to detect the items that should be in short corrected in the park. As said before photos showing disapproving opinions are seldom shared, if not used specifically for critical purposes. This category gains its entire sense in connection with what is typical; can be something disgusting typical? The unpleasant has to do with destroyed nature (forest fires), trash and junk in fields (see Photo 8), buildings in bad condition or the use of non-traditional materials (like granite, tiles and wood) in construction. It is very easy to find these kind of images all around the country in Galicia (and less in Portugal). The ideal image of the countryside based on the consecution of a harmony between humans and environment is here visually broken with a very pragmatic use of material: recycled and cheap construction materials are often used with a logic that denies the aesthetic values behind perception of rural landscape. In fact we would say, for local inhabitants this image reproduces nature in production, and beautiful is that what produces some tangible good. All the unproductive things, in these terms, have no value. Landscape representations in touristic are definitely based on the romantic perception of rural landscape.

Photo 8: Junk and gate to the field by Eiras, 2009 ©

This use of environment without ideal aesthetic value is considered one of the typical characteristic of Galician mentality, in the last years a neologism was created to give name to this phenomenon: *feísmo* (uglification) (Baamonde). Due its impact in tourism and rejection of this practice by part of the population, uglification is subject of research, Internet forums, publications and diverse initiatives (“El feísmo en Galicia”; “Consello da Cultura Galega”). Initiatives like the one lead by the most important regional newspaper, La Voz de Galicia, has a section in its online publication where readers can send photos showing examples of uglification.

- Typical (reinforcing icons): Typical is not the same than picturesque, because uglification plays an important role in the construction of Galician identity (Gondar) Typical can be either nice or unpleasant, as blend of positive and negative perceived elements. Under this category the images can be placed into these two main lines, but in some examples without a clear splitting line. Now animals are again present, but not as evidence of the biodiversity and biological interest of the park: common cattle (cows, goats and donkeys) gain the attention of hikers. They are animals easy to find, to photograph and normally they are contextualized in a surrounding environment with other elements that compose a wider landscape view. They are common animals in common situations, an image of the role of in everyday rural lives; it seems that more that the animals themselves, interesting is their evocation of farming and rural ways of living. Furthermore, architectonical elements are also taken into consideration: examples of vernacular architecture (houses, granaries, fountains, stone walls...) in use or abandoned but full of romantic land; vernacular buildings with additions of new or recycled materials (uglification); photographs of fields as samples of humanized environment but in harmony with nature (in these photos there are no traces of uglification); close views of vegetation, in many cases of wild yellow gorse – *ulex europaeus* – used in traditional farming and very common at the mountains, and very appreciated as wild flower, specially in spring when the country side is covered with it yellow flowers; stone walls, widely used to divide the small slots for agriculture; junk (pieces and refuse of clothes, engines, construction materials, empty cans, etc); and wind farms. Wind farms have become in the last century a symbol (quasi a brand) of our mountains, in many areas of highlands (a big portion of the country) the top of the hills are crowned with windmills along kilometers. Thus the wind parks can be seen from very far distances, dominating the landscape. In short, with exception of cattle, all the other motives could been found in the other two categories (nice and unpleasant).

Photo 9: Wind farm by Marco Quintas, 2009 ©

Photo 10: Granery by Pamela Pérez, 2009 ©

Promotional landscape is here enhanced with complementary visions, values, meanings and photos of environment, other or richer landscapes are created. Visitors offer their personal interpretation of the canonical landscape, giving us an evaluation of its aesthetic value and showing us a more complex and useful view of the park, moving from landscape to multi-landscape.

4. Further application in outdoor touristic promotion

Some months after these photo-taking actions we have used this initial experience to elaborate a plan of outdoor tourism promotion based on the web 2.0. Some contextualization is needed here: hiking in Galicia is characterized by three facts: (i) as a popular outdoor activity that is relatively new in Galicia due to the lack of a walking tradition (or the rejection of this tradition till nowadays), (ii) the existing hiking routes have a shortage of maintenance and of information, (iii) visitors are often giving a different value to the territory (creating a landscape), and sometimes it is contradictory to the value attributed by the touristic promoters.

The basic ideas are: (i) to move the information on the hiking routes to a web accessible to the general public, (ii) to turn the visitor into the main generator of representations of territory (from user/touristic consumer to creator) by sharing photographs, avoiding institutional promotion and representations, (iii) to create a feedback service between users, inhabitants and touristic promoters in order to redefine landscape. The tools used for those purposes are: Wikiloc, Panoramio and Wikipedia.

Our goals to contribute: (i) to build between visitors and touristic promoters a hiking culture and route net in Galicia, (ii) to redefine landscape to be attractive as outdoor touristic resource helping to the preservation of heritage (what elements of the 'natural' heritage – forests, historical roads and tracks, peasant architecture, etc.) are in danger due the lack of perception of their value, (iii) to the creation of a tourism with low environmental impact, and (iv) to detect whatever may be newly considered heritage of interest and what elements of actual perception of landscape and heritage may be in risk of extinction.

Note

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